

POTENTIAL OF NANOPARTICLES IN REFRIGERATION SYSTEM WITH NATURAL REFRIGERANT - A REVIEW

Kumbhar Anil Hiralal^a, Dr. Mohammed Ali^b

(a) Research Scholar, Mechanical Engineering Department, Oriental University, Indore, M.P. India.

Email: anil2929@gmail.com

(b) Professor and Head, Mechanical Engineering Department, Oriental University, Indore, M.P. India

Email: hasnaat_2005@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

The performance of cooling systems can be enhanced by introducing nanoparticles into compressor oils and refrigerants in refrigeration systems. This enhancement is necessary to ensure energy conservation and environmental sustainability. Nanorefrigerants/nanolubricant have emerged as a prominent application in the area of refrigeration systems, aiming to achieve higher efficiency and eco-friendly. This review aims to examine the outcomes of adding nanoparticles to lubricants or refrigerants. The application of natural refrigerants is considered ideal as they are environmentally sustainable and provide a solution to issues such as ozone depletion and global warming. In refrigeration and air conditioning applications right now, HFC refrigerants are the most effective alternative for HCFC & CFC refrigerants. The impacts of nanolubricant dispersion stabilization on tribological effectiveness and the lubrication procedures that help to enhance tribological performance are also examined in this research. In addition, this study discusses the obstacles and potential for further studies in this field. The advancement of nanorefrigerants/nanolubricant and natural refrigerants in refrigeration systems is expected to contribute to higher efficiency, reduced environmental impact, and enhanced sustainability. Further research in this field is needed to overcome obstacles and explore the full potential of nanomaterial in improving the results of refrigeration systems.

Keywords: Refrigeration, Global warming, Ozone depletion, Natural refrigerant, Nanorefrigerants, Nanolubricant.

1. Introduction

The vapour compression refrigeration method faces considerable challenges in terms of energy efficiency. Energy is extremely needed for refrigeration and other purposes. New technologies, such as nanolubricants and nanorefrigerants, however, promise to address this problem. By mixing nanoparticles with lubricating oil and basic refrigerants, nanolubricants and nanorefrigerants are produced. The dispersion of nanomaterials in these fluids offers a number of benefits, such as decreased compressor power consumption, superior heat transfer characteristics, and more powerful coefficient of performance [1]. Primary and secondary refrigerants are the two categories into which refrigerants can be divided. Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), both of which are refrigerants, are classified based on several secondary group criteria and were considered as second generation of refrigerants [2]. The potential for GWP, the potential ODP, flammable properties, phase transition enthalpy, cost, odor, and metal corrosion are some of these parameters [3]. Even though it makes up a small portion of the environment, the ozone layer is essential for preserving ecological harmony. Between 85% and 90% of the stratosphere and the troposphere are

where ozone is primarily found. Any change in the ozone percent, which varies by region from 0 PPM to 10 PPM, can have significant and immediate effects on life [4].

Preserving and protecting the ozone layer is a priority for many nations, and numerous laws and regulations related to atmospheric protection have been initialized by the European Union over the previous 30 years. These laws cover government collaboration, initiatives, and plans for controlling manufacturing development and practices. The Partnership for Appropriate Atmospheric Policy, an industry group and important advocate for ozone protection and climate change policy, provides a summary of regulations in several nations. [5]. Global warming, sometimes referred to as climate change, is another major environmental problem. Only after the start of the ozone depletion control efforts did it start to receive considerable focus. These regulations address government cooperation, projects, and strategies for policing manufacturing practices and development. The Alliance for Responsible Atmospheric Policy, a corporate company that is a major voice for ozone protection and climate change policy, provides a list of rules in various countries. [5]. Another big environmental issue is global warming, sometimes known as climate change. It didn't begin to garner much attention until the ozone depletion control efforts got underway.

International conventions requesting the phase-out of halogenated fluids have resulted from the recognition of these environmental hazards. In affluent nations since 1996 and in poor nations since 2010, CFCs have been phased out. However, due to their significant ozone depletion potential & warming potential albeit lower than that of CFCs, some HCFCs will be phased out of use in both developed and developing countries by 2020 and 2030, respectively. [7, 8, 9]. Some HCFCs were initially used as CFC substitutes Hydrofluorocarbon refrigerants have surpassed CFCs and HCFCs in refrigeration and refrigeration applications. However, concerns about their high global warming potential have prompted some European countries to phase them out as well. Hydrocarbons are being favoured as refrigerants in many European nations due to their lower environmental impact [10]. There is evidence that HFC 134a can decompose in the troposphere due to sunlight and form acidic and toxic substances [11]. If this is true, it could potentially result in another environmental tragedy worse than the CFC experience. Therefore, the use of natural refrigerants, which are already present in the bios.

Group	Refrigerant Nomenclature	ODP	GWP 20; 100; Yrs	Safety
CFC's	R11	1.00	6,300; 4,600	A1
	R12	0.95	10,200; 10,600	A1
	R113	0.85	6,100; 6,000	A1
	R114	0.70	7,500; 9,800	A1
	R500	0.70	7,700; 7,900	A1
HCFC's	R12	0.055	4,800; 1,700	A1
	R123	0.020	390; 120	A1
	R124	0.022	2,000; 620	A1
	R401A	0.037	3,300; 1,100	A1
	R5401B	0.040	3,500; 1,200	A1

Fig. 1. Effect of various refrigerant groups on atmosphere

2. Natural Refrigerant

Over the 160 years of refrigeration experience, roughly 50 distinct mixtures have been utilized pretty much generally as working media. For a considerable length of time, the vast majority of them have been dismissed as unsatisfactory; however, a sensible measure of decision exists to adjust to various execution prerequisites [10]. An assortment of regular coolants, like water, smelling salts, hydrocarbons and carbon dioxide, are among them. Options in contrast to an assortment of CFC, HCFC and HFC refrigerants are given by regular refrigerants. Notwithstanding their low ozone consumption potential and minimum or no a worldwide temperature alteration potential (Table 1).

Table 1: The impact of popular refrigerants on the environment

Refrigerant	Composition	Ozone Depletion Potential	Global Warming Potential (100 Years Prospect)
R11	CFCs	1	3800
R12		1	8100
R113		0.8	4800
R114		1	9000
R115		06	9000
R22	HCFC	0.055	1500
R123		0.02	90
R124		0.022	470
R141b		0.11	630
R142b		0.065	2000
R23	HFCS	0	11700
R32		0	650
R125		0	2800
R134a		0	1300

R143a	Natural Refrigerants	0	3800
R152a		0	140
R290		0	3
R600a		0	3
R717		0	0
R718		0	0
R744		0	1

Since regular refrigerants don't deliver molecules of chlorine or fluorine, they can't go through water responses and along these lines don't shape the subsequent solid acids that can prompt untimely disappointment of the gadget. The following is an outline of the capacity of a portion of these refrigerants as appropriate options in contrast to ozone-exhausting refrigerants and ozone depleting substances [12]. The amount of HFCs released onto the market will be steadily decreased throughout phase-down to roughly 21% of the initial amount by 2030. As shown in fig 2.

Fig.2. HFC consumption Phase-Down.

3. Methodology

Several methods for nanofluid preparation have been described in the literature, including those by O.A. Alawi, et al. [16] and Nair, et al. [17]. For instance, Peng, H., et al. [18] prepared a nanorefrigerant based on R113 refrigerant by introducing CuO nanoparticles. They measured the amount of CuO nanomaterial using a digital electronic balance and then mixed them with refrigerant R113 to get a well-dispersed nanofluid mixture through vibration for 30 minutes. Ultra sonication was used to ensure a stable dispersed solution that remained without deposition for 12 hours. A few experts combined nanofluids in two stages and one step. In the two-step procedure, nanomaterials are created and then combined with working fluid. The nanoparticles are incorporated immediately into the

operation fluid in the one-step approach. For refrigerants with a reduced normal boiling point and that are not liquid at ordinary pressure and temperature, there are two options. (i) One-step or two-step procedure for keeping refrigeration fluid at working pressure and temperature & (ii) making a nanolubricant followed by mixing with the refrigerant. Using PAG oil and ZnO nanoparticles with a size of 40 nm, Kumar, D.S. [19] created a nanolubricant. Preparation of nano refrigerant and nanolubricant will achieved by one step and two step methods with same procedure.

To avoid particle clustering, the mixture was stirred with a stirrer that was magnetic for ten hours and then homogenized using an ultrasonic sonicator for 15 hours.

Fig.3. Flowchart for producing nanofluids using one step and two step methods [34].

By using the obtained mixture to create nanorefrigerant with R152a refrigeration fluid, the energy consumption was decreased by 0.5% by volume concentration.

4. Nanofluid

The improvements in heat transfer rate of nanorefrigerants versus pure refrigerants are due to two essential elements: heat transfer area & heat transfer coefficient. [21]. Nanorefrigerants typically exhibit enhanced thermal conductivity due to the presence of nanomaterials, which increase the effective surface area available for heat transfer. Furthermore, by generating turbulence and interrupting the formation of boundary layers, nanoparticles might improve the efficiency of heat transfer in open systems such as condensers or evaporators. The use of nanorefrigerants in closed systems like refrigerators can also affect other characteristics including COP, cooling capacity and energy requirement [21]. The use of nanolubricant can also induce anomalous changes in tribological characteristics, like the lubrication qualities of the working refrigerant and rheological features of the working refrigerant [22]. Based on the most recent publications, an extensive variety of physical properties, including but not limited to electrical, mechanical, optical, acoustical, and radiological

properties, can be investigated to determine the beneficial impacts of nanomaterial in refrigerants and lubricants [24, 25]. The properties of nanorefrigerants and nanolubricant can also be influenced by a number of other factors, which have been studied in numerous publications for a variety of applications. These factors include the size and dimensions of nanoparticles, their shape, heat, aggregation, nanomaterial concentration, surfactant use, and sonication time. [26]. Understanding and optimizing these factors are important for tailoring the thermal properties and performance of nanomaterial mixture for specific purposes, and for achieving stable and reliable nanofluid preparations with minimal issues of agglomeration and sedimentation.

4.1 Significance of Nano-refrigerant on refrigeration system

Nanorefrigerants, which are created by dispersing nanomaterials at certain proportion in different types of refrigerant systems, have been studied extensively for their potential impact on energy conservation and efficiency enhancement in vapor compression refrigeration devices [1]. Tiny particles can also enhance the dissolution of the refrigerant and lubricant, acting as additives that can extend the life of the compressor [14]. Table 2 shows that researchers have been actively working on improving the thermal enhancement of nanorefrigerants. Several computer studies have been carried out to evaluate the possibility of nanorefrigerants as a substitute for standard refrigerants due to its advantages such as enhanced heat transfer coefficient and lower pressure drop. [27]. The efficiency of nanolubricant-refrigerant mixtures degrades as time passes during constantly condensation and evaporation cycles in refrigeration equipment, which can be mitigated by using a maximum lubricant quantity, a lesser nanoparticle quantity, and lower heating or cooling temperatures. Heat transfer qualities of nanorefrigerants have been examined in smooth tube and internal thread tube, with internal thread tubes having greater heat transfer properties at 0.2 wt percent concentration than smooth tubes. [29]. Research shows that the mixing of nanoparticles to refrigerants can enhance energy efficiency. For example, mixing of TiO₂ nanomaterial's in R134a refrigerant can increase the performance of refrigerators by 26.1 percent with a 0.1 percent mass fraction of nanoparticles [30]. Another study using R410a refrigerant with nanoparticles showed a 6 percent improvement in the performance of systems [31]. Nanorefrigerants have also been studied in combination with different types of lubricants and oils. For instance, the use of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles in R134a refrigerant with PAG oil resulted in a 10.3 percent reduction in energy consumption in refrigeration devices with a nanoparticle concentration of 0.2 percent [34]. Similarly, to improve COP and energy efficiency in VCR systems, a mix of TiO₂ nanorefrigerant with mineral oil or polyolester oil was investigated. [35]. Nanofluids, which are created by dissolving nanomaterial in a base fluid such as water, have also been studied for their capacity in enhancing heat transfer proportion and coefficients. Studies have shown that heat transfer proportion can be improve by 1.77-37.35 percent with the use of nanofluids, and the heat transfer coefficient can be improved by increment in nanoparticle concentration [36]. Overall, nanorefrigerants have gained attention in various area like refrigeration devices, AC, and coolants due to their potential to improve thermal and transport properties. Nanorefrigerants have been shown to decrease usage of energy by minimizing pump and compressor work, increasing heat transfer coefficients, efficiency coefficients, and freezing power, and lower discharge pressure and irreversibility, thereby improving the performance of refrigeration devices [38]. Nanorefrigerants have

the ability to boost efficiency of evaporators by improving critical heat transfer performance, which can contribute to energy conservation and efficiency enhancement in vapor compression refrigeration systems.

Nanorefrigerants have gained attention as an alternative to traditional refrigerants in a variety of disciplines, like refrigeration devices, air conditioners, and coolants, due to their potential to address some of the downsides of traditional refrigerants, like poisonous and GWP. One of the advantages of nanorefrigerants is their ability to improve the thermal and transport values of the devices they are in application. For example, nanorefrigerants can serve as more effective heat absorbers in refrigeration devices, leading to improved performance. By minimizing pump and compressor functions, nanorefrigerants can help decrease energy consumption, which can result in higher efficiency in the overall system. Moreover, nanorefrigerants have been shown to increase heat transfer coefficients, efficiency coefficients, and freezing power, while lowering discharge pressure, energy requirement, and irreversibility. This can lead to improved device performance and higher energy efficiency. Additionally, the application of nanorefrigerants can enhance the COP of the evaporator by improving critical heat flux during flow and pool boiling. This can result in improved heat transfer performance and overall system efficiency, as indicated in the literature survey you mentioned [14].

Table 2: Overlook of the nanoparticle size, nanorefrigerants and their effects.

Author	Year	Refrigerant type(R)	Nanoparticle	Nanoparticle size (nm)	Observation
Lal K., et al.[52]	2020	134a	Al ₂ O ₃	20 nm	By mixing Al ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles, Coefficient of performance of system will improve
D.S Adelekana, et al.[53]	2019	600a	TiO ₂	15nm	COP of system has highest efficiency by 0.1gram TiO ₂ nanoparticle in 40gram 600a refrigerant.
Oluseyi O. Ajayi , et al.[27]	2019	134a	Al ₂ O ₃	50 nm	COP is optimized by adding Al ₂ O ₃ particles in VCR system.
Omer A. Alawi, et al.[54]	2019	141b	Al ₂ O ₃	15nm	COP and heat transfer is increase by 15.13 % by adding nanoparticles in refrigeration system compare to pure refrigerant.
Azmi W.H., et al.[55]	2017	152a	ZnO	40 nm	Low power consumption as 21% when 21% by

					adding 0.5 vol% ZnO in R152a refrigerant
Kumar P., et al.[56]	2016	134a	Al ₂ O ₃	25 nm	Optimum result by blending 0.25 gm and 0.25 gram Al ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles in R134a refrigerant
Peng, H., et al. [29]	2017	141b	Cu, CuO, Al, and Al ₂ O ₃	-	The thermal conductivity produced by nanorefrigerants is more than that of a smooth vessel in an internal thread tube.
Zhang., et al. [30]	2018	134a	TiO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃	50nm	0.1% wt.of TiO ₂ , power requirement reduced by 26.1%. By blending 0.1% TiO ₂ in system will reduce power consumption
Dalkilic., et al. [32]	2008	12, 134a, 430a	Al ₂ O ₃	1-100nm	The COP is improved by 14.4% by blending nanoparticles in refrigerant.
Kumar, K.S., et al. [36]	2020	Al ₂ O ₃ / Nano fluid	Al ₂ O ₃	-	The use of nanorefrigerant would significantly minimize the electricity requirements of VCR systems.
Saadah, A et al. [38]	2015	R134a	Al ₂ O ₃	15 nm	COP is improved by up to 15%.

4.2 Significance of nanolubricant on refrigeration system

Nanoparticles have emerged as promising lubricant additives in recent years due to their ability to minimize friction, wear, & increase efficiency. These nanoparticles, which are typically less than 100 nm in size, may reach the contact zone and have thermal stability at high temperatures, making them appropriate for lubricant applications. [39]. Metal oxide, metal, carbonate, metal sulphides, borate, organic materials, mineral materials, and rare earth compounds have all been researched as efficient additions in reducing friction and wear. [40]. Nanolubricant, which are a new category of lubricants where nanoparticles or nanofluids are combined with the host lubricant or lubricating oil, have been revealed to improve the heat transfer efficiency of the lubricant or oil in refrigeration systems [41].

Research has revealed that the blending of nanoparticles to refrigeration systems can lead to improved performance. For e.g., in an observation by Pico et al. [42], The incorporation of diamond nanoparticles in R32 refrigerant resulted in a 0.5% increase in performance and a 5.0% improvement in refrigerating capacity. Babarinde et al. [43] observed the use of multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) nanolubricant in R600a refrigerant led to a COP increase of 2.8 with 0.6 g/l & 2.6 with 0.4 g/l, and decrease energy requirement by 0.0636 W, making it a potential replacement for R134a system. The blending of nanoparticles to lubricants has been shown to improve refrigerant solubility, reduce coefficient of friction, and lower wear rate [30]. Studies have also reported improved thermal properties and viscosity of lubricants with nanoparticles. For example, Sanukrishna and Prakash [45] observed improved rheological and thermal properties of polyalkylene glycol lubricant with TiO₂ nanoparticles at 0.6% volume fraction, which exhibited thermal conductivity and viscosity 1.31 & 10.34 times greater pure lubricant, respectively. Ohunakin et al. [46] evaluated the efficiency of Liquefied petroleum gas cooling device with nanoparticles distributed in lubricant, and reported increased COP of 2.97 with titanium oxide & 12% reduction in compressor work usage with silicon dioxide nanolubricant. Several studies have reported improved efficiency of automobile AC systems with the application of nanolubricants. For instance, Sharif et al. [48] reported a 24% increase in coefficient of performance with the application of SiO₂/PAG nanolubricant at 0.05% volume percentage in the compressor. Krishnan et al. [49] investigate that the performance of a refrigeration device can be enhanced by 21.8309% with the addition of 0.1% SiO₂ to 220 ml of PolyolEster.

Table 3: Overlook of the nanoparticle mass fraction, nanolubricant and their effects.

Author	Refrigerant Nomenclature (R)	Nanolubricant	Mass Fraction / Volume Fraction	Observation
Mendoza. et al. [42]	R32	Diamond / with POE oil	0.1% and 0.5%	COP and refrigerating capacity is improved by 0.5% and 5% by adding diamond nanoparticle.
Silva.,et al. [43]	R600a	R6000a/Multiwall carbon nanotube	0.4 and 0.6 gram/L	With 20.4 g/l cop improve to 2.6 and with 0.6 g/l COP is improved 2.8. The power requirement minimize by 0.0636 W
Zhang. et al. [30]	HFC134a	Al ₂ O ₃ , TiO ₂ with R134a	0.1 % TiO ₂ & Al ₂ O ₃ 0.06% TiO ₂ & Al ₂ O ₃ ,	TiO ₂ nanoparticle of 0.1% weight will reduce energy by 26.1 %
Gobinath, N., et al. [44]	R12	TiO ₂ with Mineral oil	0.01% TiO ₂	A reduce in the coefficient of friction outcome in an 11%

				reduction in work done by compressor.
Prakash, M.J., et al. [45]	R134a	TiO ₂ with PAG oil	0.07 % to 0.8%	TiO ₂ nanoparticle in lubricant increase heat conductivity and viscosity by 0.6%. which is more than pure lubricant
Adelekan, D.S., et al. [46]	LPG	TiO ₂ , SiO ₂ & Al ₂ O ₃ with Mineral oil	-	By blending TiO ₂ in lubricant the performance increase of 2.97 and power requirement is reduce to 13% and 12% with SiO ₂ nanoparticles.
Hussen, H.A. et al. [47]	R22	TiO ₂ with Mineral Oil	-	Compressor power minimized by 13.3% and COP improve to 11.9%.
Azmi, W.H., et al. [48]	R134a	SiO ₂ with PAG Lubricant	0.0005	At 0.05 v% concentration, there is a 24% improvement in COP.
Logesh, K., et al. [49]	R134a	Al ₂ O ₃ , SiO ₂ , ZrO ₂ and CNT with POE oil	0.1% SiO ₂ - 220 ml of POE	The performance is improve to 21% by blending 0.1% SiO ₂ particles to 220 ml POE oil

5. Conclusion

This study summarizes a large quantity of investigations on the combination of nanofluids (nanorefrigerant and nanolubricant) in the literature. Because of their better heat transfer properties and improvements in coefficient of performance and power savings, nanorefrigerants and nanolubricants are likely to be used in a variety of current refrigeration systems and devices sooner rather than later. Furthermore, nanoparticles as additives can increase heat transfer by improving thermal conductivities of heat transfer. The influence of viscosity, on the other hand, must be watched because a minor increase in viscosity can impede the operation of the refrigeration system. Nanolubricants have strong tribological qualities, which allow them to minimize friction, wear, and promote lubrication. Lubrication to get the greatest performance gain, the proper concentration of nanoparticles dispersed in base fluid must be researched. Recently, graphene and graphene oxide

nanofluids have received special attention; therefore, rigorous study into graphene and graphene oxide nanorefrigerant or nanolubricant is required.

References

1. Patil, Pradip Kailas, Rishi Dewangan, and Hemant Krishnarao Wagh. "Performance Of A Vapour Compression Refrigeration System Using Different Concentrations Of Go Nanolubricants And A Safe Charge Of R600a Refrigerant." *Migration Letters* 21, no. S3 (2024): 1337-1345.
2. Said, Zafar, Shek MA Rahman, Maham A. Sohail, Ammar M. Bahman, Mohammad A. Alim, Saboor Shaik, Ali M. Radwan, and Ibrahim I. El-Sharkawy. "Nano-refrigerants and nano-lubricants in refrigeration: synthesis, mechanisms, applications, and challenges." *Applied Thermal Engineering* (2023): 121211.
3. Islam, Md Amirul, Sourav Mitra, Kyaw Thu, and Bidyut Baran Saha. "Study on thermodynamic and environmental effects of vapor compression refrigeration system employing first to next-generation popular refrigerants." *International Journal of Refrigeration* 131 (2021): 568-580.
4. Yang, Liu, Weikai Ji, Mao Mao, and Jia-nan Huang. "An updated review on the properties, fabrication and application of hybrid-nanofluids along with their environmental effects." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 257 (2020): 120408.
5. Manirathnam, A. S., K. Senthil Kumar, R. Prabhu, M. Sivashankar, and N. Hariharan. "Experimental study of the performance of Al₂O₃/water nanofluid in condensing unit of air conditioner." *Materials Today: Proceedings* 33 (2020): 208-213.
6. Pico, David Fernando Marcucci, Leonardo Rosa Ribeiro da Silva, Oscar Saul Hernandez Mendoza, and Enio Pedone Bandarra Filho. "Experimental study on thermal and tribological performance of diamond nanolubricants applied to a refrigeration system using R32." *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 152 (2020): 119493.
7. Babarinde, T. O., S. A. Akinlabi, and D. M. Madyira. "Energy performance evaluation of R600a/MWCNT-nanolubricant as a drop-in replacement for R134a in household refrigerator system, *Energy Reports*, Vol. 6 (2),(2020), 639-647." 639-647.
8. Paul, Gayatri, Subhasis Shit, Harish Hirani, Tapas Kuila, and N. C. Murmu. "Tribological behavior of dodecylamine functionalized graphene nanosheets dispersed engine oil nanolubricants." *Tribology International* 131 (2019): 605-619.
9. Alawi, Omer A., Jassim Mohammed Salih, and A. R. Mallah. "Thermo-physical properties effectiveness on the coefficient of performance of Al₂O₃/R141b nano-refrigerant." *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer* 103 (2019): 54-61.

10. Bhattad, Atul, Jahar Sarkar, and Pradyumna Ghosh. "Improving the performance of refrigeration systems by using nanofluids: A comprehensive review." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 82 (2018): 3656-3669.
11. Minea, Alina Adriana, and SM Sohel Murshed. "A review on development of ionic liquid based nanofluids and their heat transfer behavior." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 91 (2018): 584-599.
12. Estelle Patrice, David Cabaleiro, Gawel Zyla, Luis Lugo, S.M. Sohel Murshed, Current trends in surface tension and wetting behavior of nanofluids, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 94, (2018), PP 931-944, ISSN 1364-0321,
13. Mahian, Omid, Lioua Kolsi, Mohammad Amani, Patrice Estellé, Goodarz Ahmadi, Clement Kleinstreuer, Jeffrey S. Marshall et al. "Recent advances in modeling and simulation of nanofluid flows-Part I: Fundamentals and theory." *Physics reports* 790 (2019): 1-48.
14. Sanukrishna, S. S., and M. Jose Prakash. "Experimental studies on thermal and rheological behaviour of TiO₂-PAG nanolubricant for refrigeration system." *International Journal of Refrigeration* 86 (2018): 356-372.
15. Krishnan, R.S., Arulprakasajothi, M., Logesh, K., Raja, N.D. and Rajendra, M., 2018. Analysis and feasibility of nano-lubricant in vapour compression refrigeration system. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 5(9), pp.20580-20587.
16. S. S., S., A. S., V. & M., J.P. Nanorefrigerants for energy efficient refrigeration systems. *J Mech Sci Technol* 31, 3993–4001 (2017).
17. Ajayi, Oluseyi O., Dorothy E. Ibia, Mercy Ogbonnaya, Ameh Attabo, and Agarana Michael. "CFD analysis of nanorefrigerant through adiabatic capillary tube of vapour compression refrigeration system." *Procedia manufacturing* 7 (2017): 688-695.
18. Lin, Lingnan, Hao Peng, Zheng Chang, and Guoliang Ding. "Experimental investigation on TiO₂ nanoparticle migration from refrigerant–oil mixture to lubricating oil during refrigerant dryout." *International Journal of Refrigeration* 77 (2017): 75-86.
19. Yang, Di, Bin Sun, Hongwei Li, Chao Zhang, and Ying Liu. "Comparative study on the heat transfer characteristics of nano-refrigerants inside a smooth tube and internal thread tube." *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 113 (2017): 538-543.
20. Ohunakin, Olayinka S., Damola S. Adelekan, Taiwo O. Babarinde, Richard O. Leramo, Fidelis I. Abam, and Charles D. Diarra. "Experimental investigation of TiO₂-, SiO₂-and Al₂O₃-lubricants for a domestic refrigerator system using LPG as working fluid." *Applied Thermal Engineering* 127 (2017): 1469-1477.

21. Sharif, M. Z., W. H. Azmi, A. A. M. Redhwan, R. Mamat, and T. M. Yusof. "Performance analysis of SiO₂/PAG nanolubricant in automotive air conditioning system." *international journal of refrigeration* 75 (2017): 204-216.
22. Azmi, W. H., M. Z. Sharif, T. M. Yusof, Rizalman Mamat, and A. A. M. Redhwan. "Potential of nanorefrigerant and nanolubricant on energy saving in refrigeration system—A review." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 69 (2017): 415-428.
23. Redhwan, A. A. M., W. H. Azmi, M. Z. Sharif, and R. Mamat. "Development of nanorefrigerants for various types of refrigerant based: A comprehensive review on performance." *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer* 76 (2016): 285-293.
24. Nair, Vipin, P. R. Tailor, and A. D. Parekh. "Nanorefrigerants: A comprehensive review on its past, present and future." *International journal of refrigeration* 67 (2016): 290-307.
25. Rasheed, Abdul Khaliq, M. Khalid, W. Rashmi, T. C. S. M. Gupta, and A. Chan. "Graphene based nanofluids and nanolubricants—Review of recent developments." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 63 (2016): 346-362.
26. Dai, Wei, Bassem Kheireddin, Hong Gao, and Hong Liang. "Roles of nanoparticles in oil Lubrication, Tribology International." (2016).
27. Alawi, Omer A., Nor Azwadi Che Sidik, and A. Sh Kherbeet. "The effects of nanolubricants on boiling and two phase flow phenomena: a review." *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer* 75 (2016): 197-205.
28. Kushwaha, Pravesh Kumar, Pavan Shrivastava, and Ashish Kumar Shrivastava. "Experimental study of nanorefrigerant (R134a+ Al₂O₃) based on vapor compression refrigeration system." *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering* 4, no. 3 (2016).
29. Aktas, Melih, Ahmet Selim Dalkilic, Ali Celen, Alican Cebi, Omid Mahian, and Somchai Wongwises. "A theoretical comparative study on nanorefrigerant performance in a single-stage vapor-compression refrigeration cycle." *Advances in Mechanical Engineering* 7, no. 1 (2015): 138725.
30. Mahbubul, I. M., A. Saadah, R. Saidur, M. A. Khairul, and A. Kamyar. "Thermal performance analysis of Al₂O₃/R-134a nanorefrigerant." *International Journal of heat and Mass transfer* 85 (2015): 1034-1040.
31. Shahnazar, Sheida, Samira Bagheri, and Sharifah Bee Abd Hamid. "Enhancing lubricant properties by nanoparticle additives." *International journal of hydrogen energy* 41, no. 4 (2016): 3153-3170.
32. Sarbu, Ioan. "A review on substitution strategy of non-ecological refrigerants from vapour compression-based refrigeration, air-conditioning and heat pump systems." *International Journal of Refrigeration* 46 (2014): 123-141.

33. Alawi, Omer A., Nor Azwadi Che Sidik, and H. A. Mohammed. "A comprehensive review of fundamentals, preparation and applications of nanorefrigerants." *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer* 54 (2014): 81-95.
34. Sendil Kumar, D., and R. Elansezhian. "ZnO nanorefrigerant in R152a refrigeration system for energy conservation and green environment." *Frontiers of Mechanical Engineering* 9 (2014): 75-80.
35. Mahbulul, I. M., S. S. Khaleduzzaman, R. Saidur, and M. A. Amalina. "Rheological behavior of Al₂O₃/R141b nanorefrigerant." *International Journal of heat and Mass transfer* 73 (2014): 118-123.
36. Ali Hussen, Haider. Experimental Investigation for TiO₂ nanoparticles as a Lubricant-Additive for a Compressor of Window Type Air-Conditioner. *Journal of Engineering* 20, no. 2 (2014): 61-72.
37. Fedele, Laura, Laura Colla, Mauro Scattolini, Filippo Bellomare, and Sergio Bobbo. Nanofluids application as nanolubricants in heat pumps systems. (2014)
38. Bolaji, B. O., and Z. Huan. "Ozone depletion and global warming: Case for the use of natural refrigerant—a review." *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews* 18 (2013): 49-54.
39. Kumaresan, V., R. Velraj, and Sarit K. Das. "Convective heat transfer characteristics of secondary refrigerant based CNT nanofluids in a tubular heat exchanger." *International Journal of Refrigeration* 35, no. 8 (2012): 2287-2296.
40. Kumar, D. Sendil, and R. Elansezhian. Experimental study on Al₂O₃ -R134a nano refrigerant in refrigeration system. *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research* 2, no. 5 (2012): 3927-3929.
41. Padmanabhan, Venkataramana Murthy V., and Senthilkumar Palanisamy. "The use of TiO₂ nanoparticles to reduce refrigerator ir-reversibility." *Energy Conversion and Management* 59 (2012): 122-132.
42. Sabareesh, R. Krishna, N. Gobinath, V. Sajith, Sumitesh Das, and C. B. Sobhan. "Application of TiO₂ nanoparticles as a lubricant-additive for vapor compression refrigeration systems—An experimental investigation." *international journal of refrigeration* 35, no. 7 (2012): 1989-1996.
43. Bolaji, Bukola Olalekan. "Performance investigation of ozone-friendly R404A and R507 refrigerants as alternatives to R22 in a window air-conditioner." *Energy and Buildings* 43, no. 11 (2011): 3139-3143.
44. Subramani, N., and M. Jose Prakash. "Experimental studies on a vapour compression system using nanorefrigerants." *International Journal of Engineering, Science and Technology* 3, no. 9 (2011): 95-102.

45. Boumaza, M. "Performances assessment of natural refrigerants as substitutes to CFC and HCFC in hot climate." *International Journal of Thermal and Environmental Engineering* 1, no. 2 (2010): 125-130.
46. Wang, Ruixiang, Qingping Wu, and Yezheng Wu. "Use of nanoparticles to make mineral oil lubricants feasible for use in a residential air conditioner employing hydro-fluorocarbons refrigerants." *Energy and Buildings* 42, no. 11 (2010): 2111-2117.
47. Peng, Hao, Guoliang Ding, Weiting Jiang, Haitao Hu, and Yifeng Gao. "Heat transfer characteristics of refrigerant-based nanofluid flow boiling inside a horizontal smooth tube." *International journal of refrigeration* 32, no. 6 (2009): 1259-1270.
48. Bi, Sheng-shan, Lin Shi, and Li-li Zhang. "Application of nanoparticles in domestic refrigerators." *Applied Thermal Engineering* 28, no. 14-15 (2008): 1834-1843.
49. Youbi-Idrissi, Mohammed, and Jocelyn Bonjour. "The effect of oil in refrigeration: Current research issues and critical review of thermodynamic aspects." *International Journal of Refrigeration* 31, no. 2 (2008): 165-179.
50. Pawel Keblinski, Jeffrey A. Eastman, David G. Cahill, *Nanofluids for thermal transport*, *Materials Today*, Volume 8, Issue 6, (2005), PP 36-44, ISSN 1369-7021,
51. United Nations Environment Programme. Ozone Secretariat, *Handbook for the International Treaties for the Protection of the Ozone Layer: The Vienna Convention (1985), the Montreal Protocol (1987)*. 2003, UNEP/Earthprint.
52. Eng, Dip Mech, and F. AIRAH. *Air Conditioning and Refrigeration Industry Refrigerant Selection Guide-2003*. Australian Institute of Refrigeration, Air-Conditioning and Heating Incorporated, 2002.
53. Radermacher R., K Kim, *Domestic refrigerators: recent developments*, *International Journal of Refrigeration*, Volume 19, Issue 1, (1996), PP 61-69, ISSN 0140-7007,
54. Lorentzen, Gustav, and Jostein Pettersen. "A new, efficient and environmentally benign system for car air-conditioning." *International journal of refrigeration* 16, no. 1 (1993): 4-12.